

Reducing hydrogen consumption in diesel hydrotreating

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Abstract

Due to stringent environmental emission norms, the demand for clean middle distillates is increasing in India. Refineries are focusing on production of Euro V/VI diesel using improved process and catalysts. Researchers and refiners are working on identification of cost effective processes for production of Euro V/VI diesel with minimum investment. The quality of diesel fuel is being improved by treating it with hydrogen in a hydroprocessing reactor where sulfur compounds present in diesel fraction are removed through hydrodesulphurization (HDS) reactions in the form of hydrogen sulfide. Along with HDS reactions, hydrodearomatization reactions are also taking place where aromatics rings are getting saturated by hydrogen and cetane number of final diesel products are improved. The costliest utility in the refinery hydroprocessing units is hydrogen. So the reduction of hydrogen in hydrotreating process increase the profitability of the process.

Raw diesel consists of various types of sulfur compounds, such as, thiophenes, dibenzothiophenes (DBT), 4,6- dimethyl dibenzothiophenes (4,6 – DMDBT) etc. For the production of Euro V/VI diesel with less than 10 ppm of sulfur content, it is mandatory to remove the sterically hindered 4,6 – DMDBTs. The removal of 4,6-DMDBTs happens through hydrogenation route where one aromatic ring gets saturated losing its steric hindrance before removal of sulfur. Relatively high partial pressures of hydrogen are required for the removal of 4,6 – DMDBT through hydrogenation route. Other aromatic compounds also get saturated under high partial pressures and increases the hydrogen consumption of the process which actually increases the operating cost.

To tackle this issue, Research and Development Centre of Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited (HPCL) has investigated a process of fractionating diesel in two boiling ranges and treating them separately under different process conditions to optimize hydrogen consumption and process conditions. As the boiling point of 4,6 – DMDBT is around 364°C, the raw diesel has been fractionated and divided into two fractions in such a way that higher boiling fraction which is comparatively lower in volume but contains mostly all of 4,6 – DMDBTs and being hydrotreated under relatively more severe process conditions (Example: High pressure and high temperature) and lower boiling range fraction which is comparatively high in volume and contains relatively easily removable sulfur compounds such as thiophenes, benzothiophenes etc. being hydrotreated under less severe process conditions (Example: Low pressure and low temperature). After

the hydrotreating of both the fractions in two different reactors under two different process conditions, both the treated streams are being mixed further and produce final product diesel as per specifications. In this way the unnecessary hydrogenation of aromatic compounds present in the lower boiling fractions under severe process conditions which are necessary for 4,6 – DMDBT are being avoided. This process actually reduces the overall hydrogen consumption of the process with low severity operation compared to processing the entire raw diesel stream in one reactor with severe process conditions and increase the overall profitability of the refinery.

Introduction

Due to stringent environmental emission norms it is mandatory for the refiners to produce clean fuels. The challenge lies on production of clean fuel with desired specification at lowest cost. Removal of sulfur from

diesel fuel happens by reaction of hydrogen with sulfur which is called hydrodesulphurization (HDS). Hydrogen is one of the costliest utility in the refinery. Hydrogen cost is almost 3 to 4 times of naphtha cost. During the HDS of diesel, hydrodearomatization (HDA) reactions also happens simultaneously. HDA also consumes hydrogen and improves cetane number which is an indicator of fuel combustion efficiency. As per Euro V specification, diesel fuel should have less than 10 ppm sulfur and 52 cetane number. Sometimes feed stock will already have more cetane. In that case the sulfur removal is the only target. But HDS catalyst will always have some inherent properties for HDA. So it will hydrogenate aromatics which is not required. As the sulfur needs to be reduced below 10 ppm, then 4,6 – DMDBT also needs to be desulfurized. The easiest way of removing 4,6 – DMDBT is through hydrogenation route. Where initially one aromatic ring of 4,6 – DMDBT will be hydrogenated so that the steric effect of the compound will be nullified and then desulfurization reaction will happen. Those catalysts who promote hydrogenation route of 4,6 – DMDBT removal will always have high hydrogenation activity. For these catalysts, high cetane feed stock will consume unnecessary hydrogen.

In the present study, Research and Development Centre of Hindustan Petroleum Corporation Limited (HPCL) has investigated a process scheme of fractionating raw diesel which is already having high cetane number (i.e. 50) in two boiling ranges i.e. 340 Deg C – and 340 Deg C + and treating them separately under different process conditions (i.e. different temperature and pressure) to optimize hydrogen consumption. As the boiling point of 4,6 – DMDBT is around 364°C, the higher boiling fraction i.e 340 Deg C + which is comparatively lower in volume but contains mostly all of 4,6 – DMDBTs and being hydrotreated under relatively more severe process conditions (Example: High pressure and high temperature) and lower boiling range fraction i.e 340 Deg C - which is comparatively high in volume and contains relatively easily removable sulfur compounds such as thiophenes, benzothiophenes etc. being hydrotreated under less severe process conditions (Example: Low pressure and low temperature). After the hydrotreating of both the fractions in two different reactors under two different process conditions, both the treated streams are being mixed further and produce final product diesel as per specifications. Aim of this process is to reduces the overall hydrogen consumption and increase the overall profitability of the refinery.

Conventional Scheme

Proposed Scheme

Laboratory Study

Current study has been conducted in pilot plant setup given in Figure 1. It is a two reactor system. The design temperature and pressure of the reactors are 550 °C and 250 barg. Each reactor was loaded with 25 cc catalyst. Hydrogen flow maintained through MFCs make of Brooks (make) and liquid feed flow maintained through a high pressure pump make of Eldex (make) . Reactor temperatures were maintained through a bronzed line furnace to keep isothermal temperature inside the catalyst bed. Reaction product gases were measured using wet gas meter make of Ritter and composition of product gases were measured by Refinery gas analyzer (RGA). Liquid product collected in the product tank. For all the runs, material balance of the pilot plant maintained at $\pm 2\%$.

Figure 1: Experimental Set-up

Result and Discussion

Fractionation of Raw Diesel

Raw diesel (Straight run gas oil from crude distillation unit) mentioned in Table 1 has been fractionated using TBP-Potstill unit and obtained two different feed stock named F340- and F340+ where F340- is a portion of raw diesel which has FBP near about 340 Deg C & F340+ is a portion of raw diesel which has IBP near about 340 Deg C. The detailed properties of F340- and F340+ given in Table 1. The yields obtained from TBP-Potstill unit are 71.5 wt% for F340- and 28.5 wt% for F340+.

Table 1: Properties of feed stocks

Properties		Raw Diesel	*F340-	*F340+
D86	5	255.0	248.7	338.3
	50	298.2	278.8	361.3
	95	380.2	341.1	397.4
Density (gm/cc)		853.1	842.9	887.9
Cetane Number		50	52	45
Aromatics (wt%)		27.6	19.14	45.76

*F340- is a portion of raw diesel which has FBP near about 340 Deg C & F340+ is a portion of raw diesel which has IBP near about 340 Deg C.

Table 2 shows the sulfur speciation of feed stocks. It is observed that after fractionation, the F340- contains more benzothiophenic sulfur compounds whereas F340+ contains more dibenzothiophenic sulfur compounds. As the boiling point of DBT is 332 Deg C and 4.6 – DMBT is 364 Deg C so it concentrated in the heavier portion of the raw diesel and yielded in F340+ after fractionation.

Table 2: Sulfur speciation of feedstocks

	Sulfur Species (wt%)	*BT /Alkyl BT (wt%)	*DBT/Alkyl DBT (%)
Raw Diesel	1.68	53.3	46.7
F340-	1.4	81.3	18.7
F340+	2.5	0.6	99.4

*BT : Benzothiophenes & DBT: Dibenzothiophenes

Hydrotreating

Commercial Ni-Mo type of catalyst has been used for hydrotreating reactions. Raw diesel hydrotreated at 330 Deg C temperature (WABT: Weighted Average Bed Temperature) , 80 barg pressure, 1 Hr⁻¹ WHSV and 575 Nm³/m³ Hydrogen to oil ratio. The product properties listed in Table 3. It shows that sulfur has reduced to 13 ppm from 1.68 wt%. 8 units of cetane uplift has been observed. Total aromatics has come down from 27.6 wt% to 5.83 wt%. So almost 21.77 wt% of aromatics got saturated. Calculated hydrogen consumption is 0.82 kg/100kg of feed.

Table 4 summarizes product properties of hydrotreating F340- feed stocks. Experiments has been conducted at different pressure (50 barg, 60 barg, 70 barg) keeping other conditions constant. The product sulfur is low i.e. less than 10 ppm for 60 barg and 70 barg system pressure. So the optimum pressure can be fixed at 60 barg for which hydrogen consumption is 0.37 kg/100kg of feed. For these experiments, hydrogen flow was 250 Nm³/m³ Hydrogen to oil ratio which was low compared to 575 Nm³/m³ Hydrogen to oil ratio.

Table 5 shows the product properties of hydrotreating F340+ feed stocks. Experiments has been conducted at different temperature (330 Deg C, 335 Deg C, 340 Deg C) keeping other conditions constant. It has been observed that the product sulfur is low i.e. 11 ppm for 340 Deg C temperature. So this is the minimum temperature required to get desired sulfur in the product. For this condition, the cetane upliftment is 10 units with a hydrogen consumption of 1.26 kg/100kg of feed.

So the combined product of hydrotreated F340+ (Temperature 340 Deg C) and hydrotreated F340- (Pressure 60 barg) has sulfur of 11ppm and cetane of 55.4. So the product sulfur is equivalent compared to hydrotreated product sulfur of raw diesel with an overall cetane upliftment of only 5.4 units compared to 8 units in case of hydrotreated product of raw diesel. The overall hydrogen consumption for fractionated diesel streams hydrotreating is 0.62 kg/100kg. This is low compared to 0.82kg/100kg of feed which is required for hydrotreating of raw diesel. As desired cetane number specification is 52 so by avoiding unnecessary cetane upliftment, this proposed scheme saves almost 0.2 kg/100kg of hydrogen which increase the refinery profitability. This is happening because almost 71.5 wt% of the feedstock are experiencing less operating severity i.e. 60 barg compared to 80 barg which is actually reducing the aromatic saturation reactions.

Table 3: Hydrotreated product of “Raw Diesel” feedstock

Properties	*Products
Density (gm/cc)	830
Sulfur (ppm)	13
Cetane	58
H ₂ consumption (kg/100 kg feed)	0.82
Aromatics (wt%)	5.83

*Temperature: 330 Deg C, Pressure: 80 barg; H₂/HC: 575 Nm³/m³, WHSV : 1Hr⁻¹

Table 4: Hydrotreated product of “F340-” feedstock

Properties	*Products at Different Operating Pressure (Barg)		
	50	60	70
Density (gm/cc)	830.8	829.1	827.2
Sulfur (ppm)	127	10	9
Cetane Number	55	55.6	56
H ₂ consumption (kg/100 kg feed)	0.30	0.37	0.44
Aromatics (wt%)	11.13	9.23	7.57

*Temperature: 330 Deg C, H₂/HC: 250 Nm³/m³, WHSV: 1Hr⁻¹

Table 5: Hydrotreated product of “F340+” feedstock

Properties	*Products at Different Operating Temperature (Deg C)		
	330	335	340
Density (gm/cc)	854.2	854.3	853.3
Sulfur (ppm)	33	23	11
Cetane Number	55	55	55
H ₂ consumption (kg/100 kg feed)	1.23	1.24	1.26
Aromatics (wt%)	13.06	12.94	12.52

*Pressure: 80 barg , H₂/HC: 575 Nm³/m³, WHSV : 1Hr⁻¹

Conclusion

Proposed scheme shows lower hydrogen consumption to produce high quality diesel by fractionation the feed diesel streams as per their boiling range and hydrotreat them separately at different severity of operating conditions. New scheme consumes less hydrogen which increases profitability of the process. But there is requirement of fractionator, additional reactors , gas compressor etc. So the capex of the plant also will increase. So detailed techno-economic feasibility needs to be studied in future for implementation of the scheme.

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